

Mechanical properties and oxidation resistance of NbTiCrAl RMPEAs: Influence of Cr and Al additions

Spyridion Haritos Borges¹, Willian Martins Pasini², Isabela Dainezi³, Ewa Rząda², Filip Kateusz², Wojciech Polkowski², Nabil Chaia¹, Neide Aparecida Mariano¹

¹Universidade Federal de Alfenas (PPGCEM) , ²Lukasiewicz Research Network (Krakow Institute of Technology) , ³DECHEMA-Forschungsinstitut (Materials and Corrosion)

e-mail: spyridion.borges@sou.unifal-mg.edu.br

Refractory Multi-Principal Element Alloys (RMPEAs) stand out as promising candidates to replace conventional superalloys in aerospace industry, but challenges such as high density, mechanical integrity at high temperatures and oxidation susceptibility need to be addressed [1, 2]. This study explores the impact of Cr and Al on the Nb-Ti system, aiming to evaluate the mechanical behaviour and oxidation resistance while maintaining a density below 7 g/cm³. NbTi, Nb₇Ti₇Cr₂, Nb₇Ti₇Al₂, Nb₇Ti₇Cr₁Al₁ and Nb₃Ti₃Cr₁Al₁ alloys were produced by arc furnace melting and subsequently characterized by SEM/EDS and XRD. Oxidation tests were conducted at 1000°C by thermal gravimetry analysis (TGA) for up to 20h in synthetic air. The NbTi alloy exhibited the most significant mass gain, suggesting the presence of non-protective oxide layers. Conversely, alloys containing Cr and Al, which form more stable oxides, reduced the oxidation rates. The kinetic parameter (n), which defines the oxidation regime [3], exhibited a variation from 0.80 (NbTi) to 0.52 (Nb₃Ti₃Cr₁Al₁). It indicates a transition from the mixed regime to a regime closer to the parabolic one in alloys containing Cr and Al, suggesting more efficient diffusion barriers. However, cross-section analysis revealed stratified porous layer and an internal reaction zone, suggesting the predominance of the linear regime. Compression tests were carried out at room temperature and at 1000°C. The addition of Cr and Al improves the mechanical strength of Nb-Ti alloys by increasing the Young's modulus and yield strength at room temperature. However, at 1000°C, while Cr continues to strengthen the Nb-Ti matrix, Al reduces the strength.

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